

Concept Map of MetaDocencia: This is How We Are Organized

In light of the diversification and growth we experienced over the past year, at MetaDocencia we designed this concept map, a new organizational chart that institutionalizes our way of working. We did it with an efficient and versatile organizational structure in mind, capable of meeting the challenges ahead. This scheme allows us to identify levels of responsibility, while also aiming to be dynamic enough to promote collaborative work and foster commitment, trust, recognition, and growth opportunities for the people who make up MetaDocencia.

Description of the Diagram: On the left side, the Executive Team is depicted by two intersecting sets. The lower set represents the 'Project Management', and the upper one represents the 'Chair of the Advisory Committee'. Above the Executive Team, you are going to find the Advisory Committee, drawn as a pentagon since it is composed of 5 members. The Advisory Committee and the Executive Team communicate through the Chair of the Advisory Committee. The cross-cutting areas of Infrastructure, Institutional, Impact Measurement, and Communication are represented as horizontal orange

rectangles, while the pillars of Community, Training, and Contextualization are represented as vertical red rectangles, intersecting the areas. The work teams Administration and Payments (A&P), Sustainability, and People Management (PM) are represented as orange rectangles and are coordinated by the Institutional area. The Project Management oversees the Communication area (at the bottom and outermost) and the Impact Measurement area (just above Communication) and coordinates the Community pillar. The Chair of the Advisory Committee guides the Infrastructure and coordinates the Training and Contextualization pillars. Below the rectangle of Infrastructure, there is an orange square including Accessibility, a team that works on demand and is coordinated by the Infrastructure area. The intersection of the Executive Team is related to the Institutional area. The Community Guidelines encompasses the pillars, areas, the Executive Team, the Advisory Committee, and frames the entire organizational map of MetaDocencia.

How are we organized?

The Executive Team (ET) of MetaDocencia is shared. In this map, the MT is represented by intersecting sets. They have distinct roles and responsibilities, such as the supervision of specific areas, pillars, and teams. At the same time, they share both operational and strategic functions and decisions that are complementary. MT consists of 2 roles:

- Project Management (PM)
- The Chair of the Advisory Committee (ACC).

The Advisory Committee (AC) supports and enhances the work of MetaDocencia. It is composed of 5 individuals, the majority of whom are democratically elected by the established team of collaborators of MetaDocencia. Among its responsibilities, the AC develops and approves general policies related to conflicts of interest, accountability, and transparency. To learn more about MetaDocencia's governance, visit: <https://zenodo.org/records/7392334>.

At MetaDocencia, we have four **cross-cutting areas: Communication, Infrastructure, Institutional, and Impact Measurement**. In addition, three pillars of work support and represent our organization: Community, Training, and Contextualization. In this map, the areas are represented as horizontal orange rectangles, and the pillars as vertical red rectangles. The Institutional area oversees the teams of Administration and Payments, Sustainability, and People Management; the latter also collaborates with Communication to strengthen the Community pillar. On the other hand, Infrastructure is supported by Accessibility, a team composed of experts in the field who address accessibility issues as they arise in MetaDocencia in relation to the needs of the Community.

The Community Guidelines team operates on demand, according to emerging situations. However, they represent MetaDocencia's values and provide the framework for the entire organizational map of MetaDocencia.

Pillars

Training

Our education, science, and research values nurture this pillar, which is the basis of all the projects that build scientific and technical capacities in a responsible and accessible way.

Community

Our community value shares its name with this pillar, which also allows us to put into practice our integrity, wellbeing, inclusion, and diversity values. This pillar supports projects that liaise with different communities and generate networks so that the production, communication, and application of scientific and technical knowledge are globally equitable.

Contextualization

Based on our values of diversity, autonomy, and versatility, this pillar promotes the development of a Latin American perspective in all the projects where we co-create networks, learning spaces, and resources for Spanish-speaking communities.

People, teams, areas, and pillars of MetaDocencia as of April 1st, 2024

The Project Director (led by Laura Ación) is responsible for guiding and supporting the work of Impact Measurement, Communication, and Community. Meanwhile, the Chair of the Advisory Committee (led by Nicolás Palopoli) oversees Contextualization, Training, and Infrastructure. The Institutional area is co-directed by the Executive Team.

- Executive team
 - Co-Executive Direction: Laura Ación
 - Co-Executive Direction and ACC: Nicolás Palopoli

Cross-cutting areas

- Communication
 - Supervisor: Laura Ación
 - Coordinator: Laura Ascenzi
 - Members: Julián Buede
- Impact Measurement
 - Supervisor: Laura Ación
 - Coordinator: Jesica Formoso
 - Members: José Luis Villca Villegas
- Institutional
 - Supervisors: Laura Ación, Nicolás Palopoli
 - Coordinator: Paz Míguez
 - Members according to each team in the area:
 - Administration and Payments Team: Paola Lefer

- People Management Team: Romina Pendino
 - Community Guidelines
 - Coordinator: Romina Pendino
 - Members: Iván Poggio, Paola Lefer
 - Sustainability Team: responsible for managing the strategic plan, resource acquisition, and making certain decisions regarding institutional governance. The composition of this team may vary when preparing funding proposals.
- Infrastructure
 - Supervisor: Nicolás Palopoli
 - Coordinator: Irene Vazano
 - Members: María Nanton
 - Accessibility Experts (team operating on demand):
Iván Poggio, Patricia Loto

Work Pillars

- Community
 - Supervisor: Laura Ación
 - Coordinator: Laura Ascenzi
 - Members: the entire team of internal and external collaborators
- Training
 - Supervisor: Nicolás Palopoli
 - Coordinator: Paz Míguez
 - Members: Patricia Loto, Romina Pendino, Irene Vazano, Laurel Ascenzi, Sabrina López, María Nanton, José Luis Villca Villegas, Laura Ación,

Julián Buede, Mariela Rajngewerc, Iván Poggio, Paola Lefer, Jesica Formoso

- Contextualization
 - Supervisor: Nicolás Palopoli
 - Coordinator: Sabrina López
 - Members: the entire team of internal collaborators and Pollen Project.

Projects underway as of 1st April 2024

The governance of the projects engages with and relies on this organizational map, although project management may adhere to more dynamic logics. Thus, work teams are built according to the characteristics and needs that arise in each project, with the validation and support of the ET. More details about some of the following projects can be found on our website at: <https://www.metadocencia.org/proyectos/>.

Created by MetaDocencia

Accessible Open Science

- Leader: Laura Ación
- Supervisor: Nicolas Palopoli
- Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Contextualization, Training, Infrastructure, Impact Measurement, Communication, Community, Institutional, Accessibility, Community Guidelines.
- Members: Patricia Loto, Romina Pendino, Irene Vazano, Laurel Ascenzi, Sabrina López, María Nanton, José Luis Villca Villegas, Paz Míguez, Julián Buede, Mariela Rajngewerc, Iván Poggio, Paola Lefer, Jesica Formoso.

Mapping of Open Science Communities, Organizations, and Events in Latin America

- o Leader: Irene Vazano
- o Supervisor: Laura Ación
- o Members: Jesica Formoso, Patricia Loto
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Community, Infrastructure, Impact Measurement, Communication, Administration and Payments, and Accessibility.

Hive of Fellow Communities

- o Leader: Laura Ascenzi
- o Supervisor: Laura Ación
- o Members: Julián Buede, Romina Pendino
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Community, Infrastructure, Impact Measurement, Communication, People Management.

Pollen Project

- o Leader: Laura Ascenzi
- o Supervisor: Laura Ación
- o Members: Individuals participating in the Pollen Project
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Community, Infrastructure, Impact Measurement, Communication, Institutional, Administration and Payments, People Management.

Collaborative Construction of Our Governance

- o Leader: Laura Ación

- o Supervisor: Nicolás Palopoli
- o Members: Nicolás Palopoli, Irene Vazano, Laurel Ascenzi, Paz Míguez, Jesica Formoso, Romina Pendino, Iván Poggio, Julián Buede, Paola Lefer.
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Institutional, Communication, Impact Measurement

In collaboration with other organizations

NASA Earth Data Cloud

- o Leader: Patricia Loto
- o Supervisor: Nicolás Palopoli
- o Members: Jesica Formoso, Mariela Rajngewerc
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Training, Contextualization, Administration and Payments

Catalyst Project

- o Leader: Sabrina Lopez
- o Supervisor: Laura Ación
- o Involved Areas, Pillars, and Teams: Community, Training, Contextualization, Administration and Payments.

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